

ContrastMatch_ModelCreation

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0.0.1 Effect of surfactants on the thermoresponse of PNIPAM investigated in the brush geometry

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For additional details regarding the use of refnx, see the [paper](#) or [read the docs](#).

For additional details regarding the use of the freeform model, or for details regarding the usefulness of MCMC for NR analysis, see the [paper](#)

For additional details regarding MCMC (implimented via emcee), see the [paper](#) or [read the docs](#)

For additional details regarding PT-MCMC (implimented via ptmcee), see the [paper](#) or [read the docs](#)

To follow this example, run the notebooks in the following order 1. D2O_ModelCreation.ipynb 2. CM_ModelCreation.ipynb 3. MCMC.ipynb

```
[1]: %matplotlib inline
```

```
[2]: import pickle
import numpy as np
import pandas as pd
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
from scipy.stats import norm, truncnorm
import copy
import os

from refnx.reflect import SLD, Slab, ReflectModel, MixedReflectModel
from refnx.dataset import ReflectDataset as RD
from refnx.analysis import Objective, GlobalObjective, CurveFitter, PDF, Parameter, process_chain

import sys
sys.path.append('./Code')

from FreeformVFP_mod import FreeformVFP_ext
from GenericBrushObjective import background_estimator
import plottools
```

```

def unpack_values (values):
    std_norm_bounds = (-1.96,1.96) #https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/1.96
    return values[1], (values[0], values[2]), truncnorm(*std_norm_bounds,
↳loc=values[1], scale=(values[2]-values[0])/(2*1.96))

def extract_condition(path):
    return os.path.basename(path)[7:-13]

def set_param(params, pname, value):
    for p in params.flattened():
        if p.name == pname:
            p.value = p.valid(value)
            break

def save_diffev_results(fitter, save_dir):
    np.savetxt(f'{save_dir}/diffev_bestparams_{fitter.objective.name}.dat',
↳fitter.objective.varying_parameters())
    pickle.dump(fitter.objective, open(f'{save_dir}/diffev_bestobj_{fitter.
↳objective.name}.pkl', 'wb'))
    return np.round(fitter.objective.logpost(),2), fitter.objective.
↳varying_parameters()

def print_fitqual(objectives):
    for idx, objective in enumerate(objectives):
        red_chisqr = objective.chisqr()/len(objective.data.x)
        print (f"{idx}: {objective.name}, {np.round(objective.logpost())}, {np.
↳round(red_chisqr,2)}")

```

```

[3]: # Version numbers allow you to repeat the analysis on your computer and obtain
↳identical results.
import refnx, scipy
refnx.__version__, np.version.version, scipy.version.version

```

```

[3]: ('0.1.16', '1.22.3', '1.7.3')

```

We define the function that constructs the objective. For the D2O contrast this is handled by `GenericBrushObjective.make_brush_objective`, we require a modified version here.

```

[4]: def make_objective(data_name, base_structure, material, solvent, extent,
↳extent_bounds=None,
        name='untitled', base_poly_rough=1, base_poly_bounds=(0.75,
↳2), knot_num=4):

    base_structure = copy.deepcopy(base_structure)
    solvent = copy.deepcopy(solvent)
    material = copy.deepcopy(material)

```

```

data = RD(data_name)
data.mask = data.x > 0.011

non_poly_1 = material(10, 1.5)
non_poly_1.thick.setp          (vary=True, bounds=(2, 30))
non_poly_1.rough.setp         (vary=True, value=base_poly_rough,
↳ bounds=base_poly_bounds)
non_poly_1.vfsolv.setp        (vary=True, value=0.99, bounds=(0.2, 1))

knot_num = 3
# Polymer-Solvent interface (spline)
non_poly_vfp = FreeformVFP_ext(extent=extent,
                               vf=[0.01] * knot_num,
                               dzf=[1/(knot_num + 1)] * (knot_num+1),
                               polymer_sld=material,
                               name='freeform vfp',
                               left_slabs=[non_poly_1],
                               microslab_max_thickness=5)

non_poly_vfp.extent.setp(vary=True, bounds=extent_bounds)
for idx in range(knot_num):
    non_poly_vfp.vf[idx].setp(vary=True, bounds=[0,0.4])
    non_poly_vfp.dzf[idx].setp (vary=True, bounds=(0.01, 1))

solvent_1 = solvent(0, 0)
structure = base_structure | non_poly_1 | non_poly_vfp | solvent_1

# contracting the slab representation reduces computation time.
structure.contract = 2

structure.solvent = solvent

dq_res = np.mean(data.x_err / data.x) * 100
model = ReflectModel(structure, dq_type='constant', dq=dq_res)
bkg_est = background_estimator(data, 0.15)
model.scale.setp(vary=True, value=0.8, bounds=(0.7, 0.93))
model.bkg.setp(value=bkg_est, bounds=(bkg_est*0.8,bkg_est*1.2), vary=True)

return Objective(model, data, name=name)

```

Using relevant values with their 95% confidence interval from PTMCMC sampling of the dry dataset + 40°C data in both D2O and NIPAM-CM water. This should have the best shot at characterizing the silica layer and dry polymer thickness.

```

[5]: prior_values = pd.read_csv('W10_SiO2 layer parameters.csv', index_col=0,
↳ header=0,

```

```

names=['silica thick', 'silica SLD', 'silica-SiO2_
↳rough', 'silica vfsolv', 'PNIPAM thick',
      'PNIPAM SLD', 'PNIPAM vfsolv', 'PNIPAM_
↳volume'])

polymer_ads_amt, polymer_ads_amt_bounds, polymer_ads_amt_dist =_
↳unpack_values(prior_values['PNIPAM volume'])
sio2_thickness, sio2_thickness_bounds, sio2_thickness_dist =_
↳unpack_values(prior_values['silica thick'])
sio2_sld, sio2_sld_bounds, sio2_sld_dist =_
↳unpack_values(prior_values['silica SLD'])
sio2_vfsolv, sio2_vfsolv_bounds, sio2_vfsolv_dist =_
↳unpack_values(prior_values['silica vfsolv'])
si_sio2_roughness, si_sio2_roughness_bounds, si_sio2_roughness_dist =_
↳unpack_values(prior_values['silica-SiO2 rough'])

CM = SLD(0.8, 'CM solution')
CM.real.setp(bounds=(0.65,0.9), vary=True)
sio2_poly_rough = 1

```

[6]: prior_values

```

[6]:
silica thick  silica SLD  silica-SiO2 rough  silica vfsolv  \
q1           16.578260   3.293231           10.844933       0.076289
q2           18.559324   3.455169           12.826823       0.091450
q3           20.867145   3.616602           14.443033       0.107877
stdev        1.094103    0.082492           0.917883       0.008058

PNIPAM thick  PNIPAM SLD  PNIPAM vfsolv  PNIPAM volume
q1           125.240686  0.575200         0.097191       110.527870
q2           125.762557  0.589260         0.110819       111.840543
q3           126.331105  0.606567         0.121890       113.472781
stdev        0.278168    0.008002         0.006301       0.751253

```

Now we construct the substrate layer (common between datasets)

```

[7]: si = SLD(2.07, 'si')
sio2 = SLD(sio2_sld, 'sio2')
non_poly = SLD(6, 'dSurf')

# Silicon
si_l = si(0, 0)

# Silica
sio2_l = sio2(sio2_thickness, si_sio2_roughness)
sio2_l.thick.setp (vary=True, bounds=sio2_thickness_dist)
sio2_l.sld.real.setp (vary=True, bounds=sio2_sld_dist)

```

```

sio2_1.vfsolv.setp (vary=True, value=sio2_vfsolv, bounds=sio2_vfsolv_dist)
sio2_1.rough.setp (vary=True, value=si_sio2_roughness,
↳bounds=si_sio2_roughness_dist)

bs = si_1 | sio2_1

```

List what data you want to analyse. For simplicity, only a subset is selected by default.

```

[8]: # fit_names = ["W10 lowdSDS-CM 25C",    "W10 lowdSDS-CM 40C",
#              "W10 highdSDS-CM 25C",    "W10 highdSDS-CM 40C",
#              "W10 highdC12E5-CM 25C", "W10 highdC12E5-CM 40C",
#              "W08 highdCTAB-CM 25C", "W08 highdCTAB-CM 40C"]

fit_names = ["W10 highdSDS-CM 40C", "W10 highdC12E5-CM 40C"]

```

For neatness, you could set the save directory to a subfolder. For the work presented in the manuscript we use objectives optimised using PT-MCMC, but for demonstration purposes it is fine to use the differential evolution optimised profiles.

```

[9]: save_direc = './'
file_prepend = 'diffev_bestobj_'
data_direc = 'Data/'

```

```

[10]: reload_values = True
objectives = []
D20_cont_objectives = []

for fit_name in fit_names:
    d2o_name = os.path.basename(fit_name).replace('CM', 'd2o')
    d2o_obj = pickle.load(open(f'{save_direc}{file_prepend}{d2o_name}.pkl',
↳'rb'))
    D20_cont_objectives.append(d2o_obj)

    extent = d2o_obj.model.structure[3]._extent()
    obj_name = os.path.basename(fit_name)[-4]
    temp_objective = make_objective(data_name=f'{data_direc}{fit_name}.dat',
↳base_structure=bs, material=non_poly,
                                solvent=CM, extent=extent, extent_bounds=(0.
↳8*extent, 1.1*extent),
                                name=obj_name, base_poly_rough=3,
↳base_poly_bounds=[2,4], knot_num=4)
    if reload_values:
        try:
            saved_objective = pickle.
↳load(open(f'{save_direc}{file_prepend}{obj_name}.pkl', 'rb'))
            for param in saved_objective.parameters.flattened():

```

```

        set_param( temp_objective.parameters, param.name, param.value)
        print (f'reloaded previous fit for {fit_name}.')
    except FileNotFoundError:
        print (f"no saved fit found for {obj_name}, using default starting_
↪values.")

    objectives.append(temp_objective)

```

no saved fit found for W10 highdSDS-CM, using default starting values.
no saved fit found for W10 highdC12E5-CM, using default starting values.

Ensure that parameter bounds are valid (once again, useful if the old best fit has been updated with new bounds)

```

[11]: for idx, objective in enumerate(objectives):
        for param in objective.varying_parameters():
            param.value = param.bounds.valid(param.value)

```

1 Pre-optimisation Introspection

Plot objectives against data before optimisation.

Also check $\log(\text{prob})$ and χ^2 values before optimisation.

```

[12]: fig, ax = plottools.graph_plot(objective=objectives, vf_plot=True,
↪ystyle='rq4', xstyle='log', offset=0.01,
                                color=plt.cm.plasma, orientation='h')

print_fitqual(objectives)

```

0: W10 highdSDS-CM, -5260.0, 174.92

1: W10 highdC12E5-CM, 146.0, 18.54

2 Perform an optimisation with differential evolution

Useful for checking the model bounds are set correctly etc.

nits is the number of iterations per objective (will run DE nits times)

```
[13]: nits = 3
save_direc = './'

for objective in objectives:
    print('\n\n')
    fitter = CurveFitter(objective, ntemps=3, nwalkers=200)
    print('fitting: %s'%fitter.objective.name)

    best_lnprob, best_pvecs = save_diffev_results(fitter, save_direc=save_direc)

    try:
        print('starting least squares fit from initial position...')
        fitter.fit('least_squares')
        best_lnprob, best_pvecs = save_diffev_results(fitter,
↪save_direc=save_direc)
        print(f'Least Squares lnprob (from initial position): {best_lnprob}')
    except ValueError:
        print('Initial position infesible, starting with differential
↪evolution.')

    for i in range(nits):
        print()
        print(f'Starting fit {i+1}, best prob: {best_lnprob}')

        fitter.fit('differential_evolution')
        fitter.fit('least_squares')
        red_chisqr = np.round(fitter.objective.chisqr()/len(fitter.objective.
↪data.x),2)

        print(f'Finished fit with final logpost: {fitter.objective.logpost()},
↪{red_chisqr}')

        if fitter.objective.logpost() > best_lnprob: # Fit is better than
↪previous
            best_lnprob, best_pvecs = save_diffev_results(fitter,
↪save_direc=save_direc)
            print(f'Best logpost now: {best_lnprob}, {red_chisqr}')
        else: # Fit is worse than previous
            print(f'Discarding most recent fit results. Best logpost still:
↪{best_lnprob}')
            fitter.objective.setp(best_pvecs)
```

```
if red_chisqr < 1.5: # Fit is so good we can just quit now.
    print ('Terminating fit as reduced chisqr < 1.5.')
    break
```

```
fitting: W10 highdSDS-CM
starting least squares fit from initial position...
Least Squares lnprob (from initial position): -2331.56
```

```
Starting fit 1, best prob: -2331.56
```

```
211it [01:24, 2.49it/s]
```

```
Finished fit with final logpost: 643.4189431182302, 3.7
Best logpost now: 643.42, 3.7
```

```
Starting fit 2, best prob: 643.42
```

```
251it [01:44, 2.40it/s]
```

```
Finished fit with final logpost: 682.4542344098206, 2.56
Best logpost now: 682.45, 2.56
```

```
Starting fit 3, best prob: 682.45
```

```
420it [02:43, 2.57it/s]
```

```
Finished fit with final logpost: 421.31920295629675, 10.03
Discarding most recent fit results. Best logpost still: 682.45
```

```
fitting: W10 highdC12E5-CM
starting least squares fit from initial position...
Least Squares lnprob (from initial position): 710.64
```

```
Starting fit 1, best prob: 710.64
```

```
349it [02:01, 2.86it/s]
```

```
Finished fit with final logpost: 721.1361095905045, 1.8
Best logpost now: 721.14, 1.8
```

```
Starting fit 2, best prob: 721.14
```

```
291it [01:44, 2.79it/s]
```

```
Finished fit with final logpost: 720.9717062790851, 1.75
Discarding most recent fit results. Best logpost still: 721.14
```

Starting fit 3, best prob: 721.14

243it [01:27, 2.77it/s]

Finished fit with final logpost: 692.4100454005286, 2.63

Discarding most recent fit results. Best logpost still: 721.14

3 Inspection after optimisation

Depending on how many times you run DE, it is likely you will not produce the optimum profile. PT-MCMC is required to explore the solution space in these low information content curves.

```
[14]: fig, ax = plottools.graph_plot(objective=objectives, vf_plot=True,
    ystyle='rq4', xstyle='log', offset=0.01,
    color=plt.cm.plasma, orientation='h')

print_fitqual(objectives)
```

0: W10 highdSDS-CM, 421.0, 10.03

1: W10 highdC12E5-CM, 692.0, 2.63

